

Reactivity in the oxidation of benzyl ethers by *N*-bromonicotinamide in aqueous acetic acid medium

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Abstract : *N*-Bromonicotinamide (NBN) oxidation of benzyl ethers is investigated in aqueous acetic acid medium over the temperature range of 318–333 K. The reaction exhibits first order dependence on [NBN]. The order of reaction with respect to substrate is zero. It fails to induce polymerization of acrylonitrile under the experimental conditions employed. Arrhenius and activation parameters are evaluated. Effects of dielectric constant and ionic strength of the medium on the reaction rate have been studied. Oxidation products are identified. A suitable reaction scheme is proposed and an appropriate rate law is deduced to account for the observed kinetic data.

Keywords : *N*-Bromonicotinamide, benzyl ethers, kinetics, mechanism.

Introduction

N-Halogeno compounds are known to be versatile oxidizing agents¹. Kinetics of oxidation of amino acids by NBN is reported in literature². The kinetics of oxidation of benzyl ethers by *N*-bromosuccinimide, *N*-chloronicotinamide, dimethyldioxirane, diperiodatocuprate, heat-assisted persulphate, cobaltic salts, pyridinium fluorochromate have been reported earlier³. Here we report the kinetics of oxidation of benzyl ethers by NBN, which has not been reported so far.

Results and discussion

The kinetics of oxidation of benzyl ethers by NBN is investigated at several initial concentration of the reactants. Under the condition of [NBN] \ll [benzyl ether], the oxidation of benzyl ether by NBN proceeds smoothly at 55 °C in aqueous acetic acid medium. The plot of $\log(a-x)$ versus time is found to be linear ($r = >0.99$) showing a first order dependence on [NBN]. The first order rate constant does not vary with increase in initial concentration of the oxidant (Table 1). The constancy of pseudo-first order rate constant at different [substrate] at constant [NBN] indicates the reaction is zero order in [substrate] (Table 1).

Effect of [H⁺] is investigated by varying [HCl] at

Table 1. Rate constants for the oxidation of benzyl ether by NBN at 328 K

[Benzyl butyl ether] = 4.0×10^{-2} M, [NBN] = 3.0×10^{-3} M,
[Na₂SO₄] = 1.0×10^{-1} M, Solvent (v/v) =
70% CH₃COOH - 30% H₂O

[Benzyl ether] $\times 10^2$ M	[NBN] $\times 10^3$ M	Acetic acid % (v/v)	[Na ₂ SO ₄]	$k_{\text{obs}} \times 10^4$ (s ⁻¹)
3.0	3.0	70–30	0.00	6.25
4.0	3.0	70–30	0.00	6.21
5.0	3.0	70–30	0.00	6.40
6.0	3.0	70–30	0.00	6.55
7.0	3.0	70–30	0.00	6.24
4.0	3.0	70–30	0.00	6.21
4.0	4.0	70–30	0.00	6.21
4.0	5.0	70–30	0.00	6.14
4.0	6.0	70–30	0.00	6.15
4.0	7.0	70–30	0.00	6.18
4.0	3.0	60–40	0.00	8.20
4.0	3.0	70–30	0.00	6.21
4.0	3.0	80–20	0.00	5.43
4.0	3.0	90–10	0.00	4.28
4.0	3.0	70–30	0.03	8.12
4.0	3.0	70–30	0.05	12.01
4.0	3.0	70–30	0.08	16.50
4.0	3.0	70–30	0.10	22.60
4.0	3.0	70–30	0.13	30.75
4.0	3.0	70–30	0.15	35.66

constant concentration of benzyl ethers and NBN. There is no significant increase in the rate of oxidation of benzyl ethers with increasing concentration of [HCl]. Effect of [Br⁻] and [NA] on the rate of reaction has also been studied. Addition of KBr and nicotinamide has no significant effect on the rate of the reaction. The reaction was conducted at different ionic strength using Na₂SO₄ and keeping the concentrations of other reactants constant. Increase in ionic strength of the medium increases the rate of the reaction. The plot log (*k/k*₀) versus *I* (*I* is the ionic strength of the medium) is found to be linear with positive slope for benzyl ethers (Table 1).

Increase in percentage of acetic acid in the reaction mixture decreases the rate. Plot of log *k* versus 1/*D* (*D* is the dielectric constant of the medium) is found to be linear with negative slope for benzyl ethers. The reaction mixture fails to initiate polymerization of aqueous acrylonitrile solution, indicating the absence of free radicals.

The oxidation of benzyl ethers were studied at different temperatures (328–333 K). Arrhenius and the activation parameters were evaluated (Table 2).

Mechanism :

Under the experimental conditions Br₂, HOBr, H₂OBr⁺, NBNH⁺ and NBN itself in aqueous solutions

can be the possible oxidizing species. The oxidation of amino acids by *N*-chlorobenzamide and chlorobenzotriazole have been reported to take place through the intermediate forms of protonated species of the oxidant or molecular chlorine⁴.

The oxidation of alcohols and aliphatic ketones by *N*-chlorosuccinimide and *N*-bromosuccinimide takes place through the protonated species⁵ NCSH⁺ and NBSH⁺. In the present study, the rate is not increased much with increase in [HCl]. Hence the protonated form of the oxidant, NBNH⁺ cannot be the effective oxidizing species. A simultaneous attack of H⁺ and Br⁻ ion on the *N*-haloamide can lead to the release of molecular bromine, as in the case of oxidation of amino acids by NCN. HOCl acts as the effective species in the oxidations of aliphatic alcohols by NCN⁶.

In the present investigation, the reaction is not catalysed by H⁺ and Br⁻, as the reaction rate is not increased with the increase in [HCl] and [KBr]. Taking into considerations the set of kinetic data presented above, the following mechanism may be proposed for the present oxidation study. The first step is the interaction between NBN and H₂O, which leads to the formation of the active oxidizing species H₂OBr⁺. H₂OCl⁺ is the active oxidiz-

Table 2. Rate constants for the oxidation of benzyl ethers by NBN and activation parameters

[Benzyl ether] = 4.0 × 10⁻² M, [NBN] = 3.0 × 10⁻³ M, [HCl] = 1.0 × 10⁻¹ M, Solvent (v/v) = 70% CH₃COOH – 30% H₂O

Substrate	<i>k</i> _{obs} × 10 ⁴ (s ⁻¹)				<i>E</i> _a (kJ mol ⁻¹)	Δ <i>H</i> [#] (kJ mol ⁻¹)	Δ <i>S</i> [#] (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	Δ <i>G</i> [#] (kJ mol ⁻¹)
	318 K	323 K	328 K	333 K				
Benzyl	3.47	4.03	6.21	8.59	18.17	15.44	-273.66	105.53
<i>n</i> -butyl ether								
Benzyl	3.33	5.75	6.90	9.82	19.82	17.09	-273.18	106.70
sec-butyl ether								
Benzyl	3.72	5.78	5.83	10.04	17.79	15.05	-273.33	104.72
iso-butyl ether								
Benzyl	3.18	5.71	6.02	9.32	18.77	16.04	-274.70	106.14
tert-butyl ether								
Benzyl	4.22	7.30	8.09	12.74	18.84	16.07	-271.70	105.19
<i>n</i> -propyl ether								
Benzyl	4.29	7.29	8.63	11.16	18.79	15.46	-272.20	105.40
iso-propyl ether								
Benzyl	4.42	6.60	9.02	12.74	18.84	16.12	-272.40	105.16
ethyl ether								
Benzyl	3.42	4.98	7.76	9.48	20.63	17.90	-271.19	106.86
hexyl ether								

ing species in the oxidation of maleic and crotonic acids by *N*-chlorosuccinimide¹⁶, which follows zero order kinetics in [substrate] and [H⁺]. H₂OBr⁺ reacts with the substrate in the slow step⁷. A similar mechanism has also been observed for the oxidation of L-threonine by sodium *N*-chloro-*p*-toluenesulfonamide⁸.

Mechanism :

$$\text{Rate} = k_2[\text{H}_2\text{OBr}^+][\text{substrate}]$$

Applying steady state approximation to H₂OBr⁺, the following rate law is obtained.

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{k_2 k_1 [\text{NBN}][\text{H}_2\text{O}][\text{substrate}]}{k_{-1}[\text{C}_5\text{H}_4\text{NCONH}^+] + k_2[\text{substrate}]}$$

$k_{-1} \ll k_2$

$$\text{Rate} = k_1[\text{NBN}]$$

The above mechanism explains the first order behavior of oxidation with respect to [NBN].

The structure of the complex and the formation of the products from it are given below :

A similar complex is given by Deno and Potter in the study of oxidative cleavage of ethers by aqueous bromine⁹.

Experimental

The sample of NBN used in the study was prepared² in acetic acid (Merck) and the purity was checked iodometrically¹⁰. All other chemicals were of AnalaR grade. The solutions of the benzyl ethers were prepared in acetic acid. Kinetic runs were carried out under pseudo-first order conditions ([benzyl ether] >> [NBN]).

Requisite amounts of benzyl ether, hydrochloric acid, sodium sulphate and aqueous acetic acid were taken in a jena glass reaction vessel and placed in a water thermostat maintained at the desired temperature for 30 min. The reaction was initiated by rapid addition of NBN solution and its progress was followed by estimating iodometrically the amount of unconsumed NBN at regular intervals of time.

Product analysis and stoichiometry study :

The reaction mixture containing excess of NBN over substrate (3 : 1) in the presence of HCl and Na₂SO₄ were kept at the room temperature for 36 h. Estimation of unreacted NBN showed that one mole of alcohol reacted with one mole of NBN. The overall stoichiometry of the oxidation reaction may be represented as

NA = nicotinamide

The major product of oxidation was found to be benzaldehyde. A mixture of benzyl ether (0.04 M), NBN (0.03 M) was made up to 25 ml with water-acetic acid mixture (30–70) in the presence of HCl (0.1 M). The mixture was allowed to stand for 48 h to ensure the completion of the reaction. The residual mixture was then extracted with ether. The ether layer was separated and dried. Formation of benzaldehyde was confirmed by the addition of 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine. The aldehyde was converted to 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone. The melting point of 2,4-DNP derivative is 253 °C (lit. m.p. 248 °C).

References

1. R. Filler, *Chem. Rev.*, 1963, 63, 21.
2. L. Pushpalatha and K. Vivekanandan, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2008, 85, 1027.
3. N. Mathiyalagan and R. Sridharan, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2006, 83, 434; N. Mathiyalagan, V. Priya and J. John Bosco, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2009, 86, 453; S. A. Grabovskiy, Q. K. Timerghazin, N. N. Kabal'nova, *Russian Chemical Bulletin*, 2005, 54, 2384; Jin-huan Shan, Li-ping Wang, Shigang Shen and Han-wen Sun, *Wuji Huaxue Xuebao*, 2002, 18, 887; Kun-chang Huang, Richard A. Couttenye and George E. Hoag, *Chemosphere*, 2002, 49, 413; Cooper, Terence Albert and William, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, 5, 455; A. Jagathesan, K. Nambi, S. J. Arulraj and K. A. Basheer Ahamed, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1989, 28, 904.

4. A. Lal and M. C. Agarwal, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1990, **67**, 164; S. C. Hiremath, S. M. Mayanna and N. Venkatasubramanian, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2*, 1987, 569.
5. N. S. Srinivasan and N. Venkatasubramanian, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1974, **30**, 419; Bharat Singh, Lalji Pandey, J. Sharma and S. M. Pandey, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1982, **38**, 69.
6. K. Vivekanandan and K. Nambi, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1999, **76**, 98; N. Mathiyalagan, R. Sridharan and V. Priya, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2006, **82**, 795.
7. Ashish, Chhaya Singh, Ashok Kumar Singh and Bharat Singh, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2005, **44**, 476.
8. D. S. Mahadevappa, K. S. Rengappa and N. M. M. Gowda, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1981, **85**, 3651.
9. N. C. Deno and Neil H. Potter, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **89**, 3550.
10. N. K. Mathur and C. K. Narang, "The Determination of Organic Compounds with *N*-Bromosuccinimide", Academic Press, New York, 1975.